

**Modified Technique for Type-2 Neutrosophic Number Multiple-Attribute
Decision-Making and Applications to Quality Evaluation of Management Work
in University Student Organizations**

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Abstract: The quality evaluation of management work in university student organizations is a process of systematically analyzing and assessing the efficiency, organizational capacity, and management level of student organizations. Evaluation criteria typically cover areas such as institutional development, event planning and execution, member development and management, and resource utilization. By combining quantitative and qualitative methods, the evaluation not only identifies strengths and weaknesses in the management process but also provides a basis for future improvements and optimizations, ultimately enhancing the overall management level and work quality of student organizations. The quality evaluation of management work in university student organizations is multiple-attribute decision-making (MADM). In this study, the Exponential TODIM (ExpTODIM) approach and TOPSIS approach are proposed for multi-attribute decision-making (MADM). To address the uncertainty and vagueness in the quality evaluation of management work in university student organizations, Type-2 Neutrosophic Numbers (T2NNs) are utilized to represent fuzzy information. The study introduces the T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS approach for MADM under T2NNs. Numerical example is presented to validate the effectiveness of the T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS in evaluating the quality of management work in university student organizations. The primary motivations behind this research include: (1) enhancing the ExpTODIM and TOPSIS approaches by incorporating Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets (IFS); (2) using entropy to assign weight values based on score functions within the T2NN framework; (3) developing the T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS for MAGDM; and (4) conducting a numerical example and comparative analysis to demonstrate the validity of the proposed approach in evaluating management quality. Through this work, the study provides a comprehensive solution for handling complex decision-making scenarios where uncertainty and fuzziness are present, thereby improving the accuracy and reliability of quality assessments in university student organizations.

Keywords: MADM; T2NNs; ExpTODIM technique; TOPSIS technique; quality evaluation of management work

1. Introduction

In the research on university student management and organizational management, early literature primarily focused on network public opinion management and information system construction. Li and Zhang [1] analyzed the role of university student organizations in network public opinion management, highlighting the unique advantages of student organizations in information collection and event response. Wang, Yuan, and Jing [2] further proposed the construction of a student information management system in universities, using data warehouses and data mining techniques to provide more effective decision support for grassroots teaching organizations. Luo [3] explored how to improve the management efficiency of university student organizations from the aspects of institutional reform, cadre management, and cultural construction, emphasizing the importance of these factors for the development of student organizations. Fu [4] proposed a university student organization management model based on social organization management concepts, stressing the need for changes in traditional management models and multi-party collaboration. Li [5] discussed the application of corporate management models in university student organizations, noting that while this approach improves management efficiency, it also has certain shortcomings. Zhu [6] focused on the construction of student organizations in private universities, suggesting the introduction of project management theories to enhance the standardization and effectiveness of organization management. Chen [7] studied how to improve the management capacities of student organization leaders through team development theories, helping them to diagnose and solve issues within their teams autonomously. With the deepening of social and educational reforms, Zhang [8] analyzed the organizational differentiation and multi-integration issues in university student management during social transformation, proposing optimization paths such as constructing a flat organizational structure and reasonable incentive systems. Xia [9] examined the management reform of university student organizations from the perspective of organizational sociology, emphasizing the core role of ideological and political education in student organization management. Sun, Chen, Duan, Dong and Li [10] conducted a survey on the current state of student organization management in universities and proposed suggestions for optimizing management to enhance the educational effect of extracurricular activities. Based on the theory of learning organizations, Zhao [11] proposed innovations in university student education management models, advocating the

integration of self-management and lifelong learning mechanisms to promote personalized student development. Jing, Yu and Gao [12] researched student party branch management models from the perspective of total quality management, proposing improvement measures to enhance the quality of the student party member team. Deng, Wu and Zhao [13] studied the integration strategies of ideological and political education with student organization management in universities, offering various solutions to promote the overall development of students. Finally, Xiao [14] explored the application of organizational behavior theory in the management of students in applied universities, emphasizing the improvement of student management and the cultivation of applied talents through individual and group behavior research.

The quality evaluation of management work in university student organizations is MADM. In recent time, ExpTODIM [15, 16] approach and TOPSIS approach [17-19] is came up with the MADM. T2NNs [20] have been introduced to represent fuzzy information in the quality evaluation of management work in university student organizations. Despite the growing interest in MADM techniques, few studies have explored the integration of ExpTODIM and TOPSIS methods within an entropy model using T2NNs. To address this gap, the T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS model is proposed as a novel approach to MADM, incorporating T2NNs to handle uncertainty and fuzziness in decision-making processes. A numerical example, along with a comparative analysis, is presented to validate the effectiveness of the T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS model for evaluating the quality of management in university student organizations. The primary motivations for this research are outlined: (1) the ExpTODIM and TOPSIS methods are enhanced through the application of T2NNs, allowing for more accurate portrayal of uncertainty and decision-makers' psychological behaviors; (2) entropy is utilized to assign weight values based on score functions, further refining the decision-making process when combined with T2NNs; (3) the T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS model provides a comprehensive framework for MADM, effectively integrating multiple decision-making approaches; and (4) the numerical example and comparative analysis confirm the validity of the proposed model, demonstrating its capability to handle complex evaluation scenarios. In conclusion, the T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS model offers a robust and reliable tool for quality evaluation in university student organizations, addressing both uncertainty and fuzziness in decision-making. By combining the strengths of ExpTODIM, TOPSIS, and entropy models with T2NNs, this approach

provides a more nuanced and effective method for handling multi-attribute decision-making problems in organizational management contexts.

The structure of this study is outlined as follows. Section 2 introduces the creation of T2NNs. In Section 3, the T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS technique is proposed for MADM alongside T2NNs. Section 4 presents a numerical analysis for evaluating the quality of management work in university student organizations, featuring various comparative analyses. Finally, Section 5 concludes the study, summarizing key findings and insights. This structure ensures a comprehensive exploration of the topic, highlighting the development and application of advanced models for effective decision-making and quality evaluation in organizational management.

2. Preliminaries

Wang et al. [21] constructed the SVNNS

Definition 1 [21]. The SVNNS is constructed:

$$VA = \{(\theta, VT_{VA}(\theta), VI_{VA}(\theta), VF_{VA}(\theta)) | \theta \in \Theta\} \quad (1)$$

where $VT_{VA}(\theta), VI_{VA}(\theta), VF_{VA}(\theta)$ is truth-membership (TM), indeterminacy-membership (IM)

and falsity-membership (FM), $VT_{VA}(\theta), VI_{VA}(\theta), VF_{VA}(\theta) \in [0, 1]$,

$0 \leq VT_{VA}(\theta) + VI_{VA}(\theta) + VF_{VA}(\theta) \leq 3$. The SVNNS is depicted as $VA = (VT_A, VI_A, VF_A)$, where

$VT_A, VI_A, VF_A \in [0, 1]$, and $0 \leq VT_A + VI_A + VF_A \leq 3$.

Abdel-Basset et al. [20] constructed the T2NNs.

Definition 1[20]. The T2NN is constructed:

$$VV = \{(\theta, VT(\theta), VI(\theta), VF(\theta)) | \theta \in \Theta\} \quad (2)$$

where $VT(\theta), VI(\theta), VF(\theta) \in [0, 1]$ be TM, IM and FM which is constructed through triangular fuzzy numbers.

$$VT(\theta) = (VT^L(\theta), VT^M(\theta), VT^U(\theta)), 0 \leq VT^L(\theta) \leq VT^M(\theta) \leq VT^U(\theta) \leq 1 \quad (3)$$

$$VI(\theta) = (VI^L(\theta), VI^M(\theta), VI^U(\theta)), 0 \leq VI^L(\theta) \leq VI^M(\theta) \leq VI^U(\theta) \leq 1 \quad (4)$$

$$VF(\theta) = (VF^L(\theta), VF^M(\theta), VF^U(\theta)), 0 \leq VF^L(\theta) \leq VF^M(\theta) \leq VF^U(\theta) \leq 1 \quad (5)$$

We let $VV = \{(VT^L, VT^M, VT^U), (VI^L, VI^M, VI^U), (VF^L, VF^M, VF^U)\}$ be a T2NN,

$0 \leq VT^U + VI^U + VF^U \leq 3$.

Definition 2[20]. Let $VV_1 = \{(VT_1^L, VT_1^M, VT_1^U), (VI_1^L, VI_1^M, VI_1^U), (VF_1^L, VF_1^M, VF_1^U)\}$, $VV_2 = \{(VT_2^L, VT_2^M, VT_2^U), (VI_2^L, VI_2^M, VI_2^U), (VF_2^L, VF_2^M, VF_2^U)\}$ and $VV = \{(VT^L, VT^M, VT^U), (VI^L, VI^M, VI^U), (VF^L, VF^M, VF^U)\}$ be TFNNs, several operation laws are constructed:

$$(1) VV_1 \oplus VV_2 = \left\{ \left(VT_1^L + VT_2^L - VT_1^L VT_2^L, VT_1^M + VT_2^M - VT_1^M VT_2^M, VT_1^U + VT_2^U - VT_1^U VT_2^U \right), \left(VI_1^L VI_2^L, VI_1^M VI_2^M, VI_1^U VI_2^U \right), \left(VF_1^L VF_2^L, VF_1^M VF_2^M, VF_1^U VF_2^U \right) \right\};$$

$$(2) VV_1 \otimes VV_2 = \left\{ \left(VT_1^L VT_2^L, VT_1^M VT_2^M, VT_1^U VT_2^U \right), \left(VI_1^L + VI_2^L - VI_1^L VI_2^L, VI_1^M + VI_2^M - VI_1^M VI_2^M, VI_1^U + VI_2^U - VI_1^U VI_2^U \right), \left(VF_1^L + VF_2^L - VF_1^L VF_2^L, VF_1^M + VF_2^M - VF_1^M VF_2^M, VF_1^U + VF_2^U - VF_1^U VF_2^U \right) \right\};$$

$$(3) \lambda VV = \left\{ \left(1 - (1 - VT^L)^\lambda, 1 - (1 - VT^M)^\lambda, 1 - (1 - VT^U)^\lambda \right), \left((VI^L)^\lambda, (VI^M)^\lambda, (VI^U)^\lambda \right), \left((VF^L)^\lambda, (VF^M)^\lambda, (VF^U)^\lambda \right) \right\}, \lambda > 0;$$

$$(4) VV^\lambda = \left\{ \left((VT^L)^\lambda, (VT^M)^\lambda, (VT^U)^\lambda \right), \left(1 - (1 - VI^L)^\lambda, 1 - (1 - VI^M)^\lambda, 1 - (1 - VI^U)^\lambda \right), \left(1 - (1 - VF^L)^\lambda, 1 - (1 - VF^M)^\lambda, 1 - (1 - VF^U)^\lambda \right) \right\}, \lambda > 0.$$

The operation laws have different properties.

$$(1) VV_1 \oplus VV_2 = VV_2 \oplus VV_1, VV_1 \otimes VV_2 = VV_2 \otimes VV_1, ((VV_1)^{\lambda_1})^{\lambda_2} = (VV_1)^{\lambda_1 \lambda_2}; \tag{6}$$

$$(2) \lambda (VV_1 \oplus VV_2) = \lambda VV_1 \oplus \lambda VV_2, (VV_1 \otimes VV_2)^\lambda = (VV_1)^\lambda \otimes (VV_2)^\lambda; \tag{7}$$

$$(3) \lambda_1 VV_1 \oplus \lambda_2 VV_1 = (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) VV_1, (VV_1)^{\lambda_1} \otimes (VV_1)^{\lambda_2} = (VV_1)^{(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)}. \tag{8}$$

Definition 3[20]. Let $VV = \{(VT^L, VT^M, VT^U), (VI^L, VI^M, VI^U), (VF^L, VF^M, VF^U)\}$ be TFNN, the useful SF (score function) and AF (accuracy function) are constructed:

$$SF(VV) = \frac{1}{12} \left[\begin{aligned} &8 + (VT^L + 2VT^M + VT^U) \\ &- (VI^L + 2VI^M + VI^U) - (VF^L + 2VF^M + VF^U) \end{aligned} \right], SF(VV) \in [0, 1] \tag{9}$$

$$AF(VV) = \frac{1}{12} \left[\begin{aligned} & (VT^L + 2VT^M + VT^U) \\ & + (VI^L + 2VI^M + VI^U) + (VF^L + 2VF^M + VF^U) \end{aligned} \right], AF(VV) \in [0,1] \tag{10}$$

For different TFNNs, some results are constructed from Definition 3:

- (1) if $SF(VV_1) < SF(VV_2)$, then $VV_1 < VV_2$;
- (2) if $SF(VV_1) = SF(VV_2)$, $AF(VV_1) < AF(VV_2)$, then $VV_1 < VV_2$;
- (3) if $SF(VV_1) = SF(VV_2)$, $AF(VV_1) = AF(VV_2)$, then $VV_1 = VV_2$.

Definition 4[20]. Let $VV_1 = \{(VT_1^L, VT_1^M, VT_1^U), (VI_1^L, VI_1^M, VI_1^U), (VF_1^L, VF_1^M, VF_1^U)\}$, $VV_2 = \{(VT_2^L, VT_2^M, VT_2^U), (VI_2^L, VI_2^M, VI_2^U), (VF_2^L, VF_2^M, VF_2^U)\}$ be T2NNs, the T2NN Hamming distance (T2NNHD) and T2NN Euclidean distance (T2NNED) is constructed:

$$T2NNHD(VV_1, VV_2) = \frac{1}{9} \left(\begin{aligned} & |VT_1^L - VT_2^L| + |VT_1^M - VT_2^M| + |VT_1^U - VT_2^U| \\ & + |VI_1^L - VI_2^L| + |VI_1^M - VI_2^M| + |VI_1^U - VI_2^U| \\ & + |VF_1^L - VF_2^L| + |VF_1^M - VF_2^M| + |VF_1^U - VF_2^U| \end{aligned} \right) \tag{11-a}$$

$$T2NNED(VV_1, VV_2) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{9} \left(\begin{aligned} & |VT_1^L - VT_2^L|^2 + |VT_1^M - VT_2^M|^2 + |VT_1^U - VT_2^U|^2 \\ & + |VI_1^L - VI_2^L|^2 + |VI_1^M - VI_2^M|^2 + |VI_1^U - VI_2^U|^2 \\ & + |VF_1^L - VF_2^L|^2 + |VF_1^M - VF_2^M|^2 + |VF_1^U - VF_2^U|^2 \end{aligned} \right)} \tag{11-b}$$

3. T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS approach for MADM with entropy

The T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS is constructed for MAGDM. Let $VA = \{VA_1, VA_2, \dots, VA_m\}$ be different alternative and $VG = \{VG_1, VG_2, \dots, VG_n\}$ be different attributes with weight vW , $vW_j \in [0,1], \sum_{j=1}^n vW_j = 1$. Then, T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS is constructed for MADM(see Figure 1).

Figure 1. T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS approach for MADM with entropy

3.1. T2NN-MADM issue

Step 1. Construct the T2NN-matrix $VM = [VM_{ij}]_{m \times n}$:

$$VM = [VM_{ij}]_{m \times n} = \begin{matrix} & VG_1 & VG_2 & \dots & VG_n \\ \begin{matrix} VA_1 \\ VA_2 \\ \vdots \\ VA_m \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} VM_{11} & VM_{12} & \dots & VM_{1n} \\ VM_{21} & VM_{22} & \dots & VM_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ VM_{m1} & VM_{m2} & \dots & VM_{mn} \end{bmatrix} & & & \end{matrix} \quad (12)$$

$$VM_{ij} = \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \left((VI_{ij}^L), (VI_{ij}^M), (VI_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((VF_{ij}^L), (VF_{ij}^M), (VF_{ij}^U) \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{13}$$

Step 2. Normalize $VM = [VM_{ij}]_{m \times n}$ into $NVM = [NVM_{ij}]_{m \times n}$.

Aiming at benefit attributes:

$$NVM_{ij} = \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \left((NVT_{ij}^L), (NVT_{ij}^M), (NVT_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((NVI_{ij}^L), (NVI_{ij}^M), (NVI_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((NVF_{ij}^L), (NVF_{ij}^M), (NVF_{ij}^U) \right) \end{aligned} \right\} = \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \left((VT_{ij}^L), (VT_{ij}^M), (VT_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((VI_{ij}^L), (VI_{ij}^M), (VI_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((VF_{ij}^L), (VF_{ij}^M), (VF_{ij}^U) \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{14}$$

Aiming at cost attributes:

$$NVM_{ij} = \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \left((NVT_{ij}^L), (NVT_{ij}^M), (NVT_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((NVI_{ij}^L), (NVI_{ij}^M), (NVI_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((NVF_{ij}^L), (NVF_{ij}^M), (NVF_{ij}^U) \right) \end{aligned} \right\} = \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \left((VF_{ij}^L), (VF_{ij}^M), (VF_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((VI_{ij}^L), (VI_{ij}^M), (VI_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((VT_{ij}^L), (VT_{ij}^M), (VT_{ij}^U) \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{15}$$

3.2. Construct the weight with entropy

Step 3. Construct the weight with entropy.

Entropy [22] is constructed for weight numbers. The matrix (NFDM) is constructed:

$$NFDM_{ij} = \frac{\left(\begin{aligned} & \left((NHA_{ij}^L), (NHA_{ij}^M), (NHA_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((NHB_{ij}^L), (NHB_{ij}^M), (NHB_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((NHC_{ij}^L), (NHC_{ij}^M), (NHC_{ij}^U) \right) \end{aligned} \right)_{AF} + \left(\begin{aligned} & \left((NHA_{ij}^L), (NHA_{ij}^M), (NHA_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((NHB_{ij}^L), (NHB_{ij}^M), (NHB_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((NHC_{ij}^L), (NHC_{ij}^M), (NHC_{ij}^U) \right) \end{aligned} \right)_{SF}}{\sum_{i=1}^m \left(\begin{aligned} & \left((NHA_{ij}^L), (NHA_{ij}^M), (NHA_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((NHB_{ij}^L), (NHB_{ij}^M), (NHB_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((NHC_{ij}^L), (NHC_{ij}^M), (NHC_{ij}^U) \right) \end{aligned} \right)_{AF} + \left(\begin{aligned} & \left((NHA_{ij}^L), (NHA_{ij}^M), (NHA_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((NHB_{ij}^L), (NHB_{ij}^M), (NHB_{ij}^U) \right), \\ & \left((NHC_{ij}^L), (NHC_{ij}^M), (NHC_{ij}^U) \right) \end{aligned} \right)_{SF}}$$

(16)

Fuzzy Shannon decision entropy (FSDE) is constructed:

$$FSDE_j = -\frac{1}{\ln m} \sum_{i=1}^m NFDM_{ij} \ln NFDM_{ij} \tag{17}$$

and $NFDM_{ij} \ln NFDM_{ij} = 0$ if $NFDM_{ij} = 0$.

Then, the weight numbers $vw = (vw_1, vw_2, \dots, vw_n)$ is constructed:

$$vw_j = \frac{1 - FSDE_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n (1 - FSDE_j)} \tag{18}$$

3.3. T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS technique for MADM

T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS technique is constructed for MADM.

Step 4. Construct relative weight:

$$rvw_j = vw_j / \max_j vw_j, \tag{19}$$

Step 5. Construct the T2NN dominance degree values (T2NNDDV).

(1) The T2NNDDV of VA_i for VA_t under VG_j is constructed:

$$T2NNDDV_j(VA_i, VA_t) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{rvw_j \times \left(1 - 10^{-\rho T2NNHD(NVM_{ij}, NVM_{it})}\right)}{\sum_{j=1}^n rvw_j} \right) & \text{if } SF(NVM_{ij}) > SF(NVM_{it}) \\ + \left(\frac{rvw_j \times \left(1 - 10^{-\rho T2NNED(NVM_{ij}, NVM_{it})}\right)}{\sum_{j=1}^n rvw_j} \right) & \\ 0 & \text{if } SF(NVM_{ij}) = SF(NVM_{it}) \\ \left(\frac{1}{v\theta} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n rvw_j \times \left(1 - 10^{-\rho T2NNHD(NVM_{ij}, NVM_{it})}\right)}{rvw_j} \right) & \text{if } SF(NVM_{ij}) < SF(NVM_{it}) \\ \left(\frac{1}{v\theta} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n rvw_j \times \left(1 - 10^{-\rho T2NNED(NVM_{ij}, NVM_{it})}\right)}{rvw_j} \right) & \end{cases} \tag{20}$$

where $v\theta$ is obtained from Tversky and Kahneman [23] and $\rho \in [1, 5]$ [24].

(2) The $T2NNDDV_j(VA_i)(j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n)$ under VG_j is constructed:

$$T2NNDDV_j(VA_i) = [T2NNDDV_j(VA_i, VA_t)]_{m \times m}$$

$$= \begin{matrix} & VA_1 & VA_2 & \dots & VA_m \\ \begin{matrix} VA_1 \\ VA_2 \\ \vdots \\ VA_m \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & T2NNDDV_j(VA_1, VA_2) & \dots & T2NNDDV_j(VA_1, VA_m) \\ T2NNDDV_j(VA_2, VA_1) & 0 & \dots & T2NNDDV_j(VA_2, VA_m) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ T2NNDDV_j(VA_m, VA_1) & T2NNDDV_j(VA_m, VA_2) & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

(3) Construct the T2NNDDV of VA_i for VG_j :

$$T2NNDDV_j(VA_i) = \sum_{t=1}^m T2NNDDV_j(VA_i, VA_t) \tag{21}$$

(4) The T2NNDDD matrix is constructed:

$$T2NNDDV = (T2NNDDV_{ij})_{m \times n}$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} & VG_1 & VG_2 & \dots & VG_n \\ \begin{matrix} VA_1 \\ VA_2 \\ \vdots \\ VA_m \end{matrix} & \begin{matrix} \sum_{t=1}^m T2NNDDV_1(VA_1, VA_t) \\ \sum_{t=1}^m T2NNDDV_1(VA_2, VA_t) \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{t=1}^m T2NNDDV_1(VA_m, VA_t) \end{matrix} & \begin{matrix} \sum_{t=1}^m T2NNDDV_2(VA_1, VA_t) \\ \sum_{t=1}^m T2NNDDV_2(VA_2, VA_t) \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{t=1}^m T2NNDDV_2(VA_m, VA_t) \end{matrix} & \dots & \begin{matrix} \sum_{t=1}^m T2NNDDV_n(VA_1, VA_t) \\ \sum_{t=1}^m T2NNDDV_n(VA_2, VA_t) \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{t=1}^m T2NNDDV_n(VA_m, VA_t) \end{matrix} \end{bmatrix}$$

Step 6. Construct the T2NNPIDS (T2NN positive ideal decision solution) and T2NNNIDS (T2NN negative ideal decision solution):

$$T2NNPIDS = (T2NNPIDS_1, T2NNPIDS_1, \dots, T2NNPIDS_n) \tag{22}$$

$$T2NNNIDS = (T2NNNIDS_1, T2NNNIDS_1, \dots, T2NNNIDS_n) \tag{23}$$

$$T2NNPIDS_j = \max_{j=1}^n T2NNDDV_{ij}, \tag{24}$$

$$T2NNNIDS_j = \min_{j=1}^n T2NNDDV_{ij} \tag{25}$$

Step 7. Construct the T2NNEDV (T2NN Euclidean distance values) for T2NNPIDS and T2NNNIDS.

$$T2NNEDV(HA, T2NNPIDS) = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (T2NNDDV_{ij} - T2NNPIDS_j)^2} \tag{26}$$

$$T2NNEDV(VA_i, T2NNNIDS) = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (T2NNDDV_{ij} - T2NNNIDS_j)^2} \tag{27}$$

Step 8. Construct the T2NNCCV (T2NN closeness coefficient values) for T2NNPIDS.

$$T2NNCCV(VA_i, T2NNPIDS) = \frac{T2NNEDV(VA_i, T2NNNIDS)}{(T2NNEDV(VA_i, T2NNPIDS) + T2NNEDV(VA_i, T2NNPIDS))} \quad (28)$$

$$= \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (T2NNDDD_{ij} - T2NNNIDS_j)^2}}{\left(\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (T2NNDDD_{ij} - T2NNNIDS_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (T2NNDDD_{ij} - T2NNPIDS_j)^2} \right)} \quad (29)$$

Step 9. Sort and select the optimal alternative with maximum T2NNCCV.

4. Numerical example and comparative analysis

4.1. Numerical example for quality evaluation of management work in university student organizations

The quality evaluation of management work in university student organizations is an important process of systematically analyzing, assessing, and providing feedback on various activities within the organization's management. As student organizations serve as key vehicles for campus cultural activities, their management level directly impacts the vitality and influence of the organization. Therefore, a scientific and reasonable quality evaluation system is crucial for improving the management capabilities and overall performance of student organizations. Firstly, the goal of quality evaluation is to comprehensively understand the current management status of student organizations, identifying their strengths and weaknesses. The evaluation typically covers multiple aspects, including organizational system development, event planning and execution, team building, member development and management, financial and resource management, and promotion. By conducting an in-depth analysis of these areas, it is possible to effectively assess the organization's execution, innovation, and coordination capabilities in management. Secondly, in terms of evaluation methods, universities often adopt a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches. Quantitative evaluation is usually carried out through surveys and performance indicators, such as the number of event participants, event impact, and financial status. Qualitative evaluation, on the other hand, focuses more on soft indicators of organizational development, such as team cohesion, member satisfaction, and organizational culture building. This multidimensional evaluation approach provides a more comprehensive and objective reflection of the actual operation of student organizations. Additionally, data collection during the evaluation process needs to come from multiple channels. Feedback can come not only from within the organization but also from external experts or advisors, providing more neutral and impartial opinions. Some universities may even involve third-party evaluation agencies to conduct professional management quality evaluations to ensure fairness and scientific rigor. The evaluation results are typically communicated to the leadership of the student organization and serve as a basis for future improvements and optimizations. By analyzing the evaluation report, student organizations can identify their areas of strength to further enhance them, while also

developing practical measures to address weaknesses. For instance, if the evaluation identifies shortcomings in event planning, the organization can strengthen training in this area; if member management is found to be ineffective, the organization can introduce improved incentive mechanisms and management processes. Lastly, quality evaluation is not only a summary of past work but also a guide for future development. Through regular evaluations of management work quality, student organizations can continuously optimize their operational mechanisms, improve management efficiency, and strengthen team cohesion, thereby better serving the student body and contributing to the prosperity and development of campus culture. In conclusion, the quality evaluation of management work in university student organizations is an effective means of improving organizational management levels and promoting healthy development. It is also a key way of cultivating students' leadership and management skills. The quality evaluation of management work in university student organizations is MADM. Five potential regional comprehensive universities $VA_i (i=1,2,3,4,5)$ to assessed through different attributes: ①VG₁ is Organizational System Development: This indicator assesses the degree of institutionalized management within the student organization, including the completeness, enforceability, and standardization of organizational charters, rules, and internal management processes. A well-established system ensures the orderly execution of organizational tasks and enhances members' sense of participation and responsibility. ②VG₂ is Event Planning and Execution: This indicator evaluates the organization's ability to plan, organize, and execute events. It includes aspects such as the creativity, impact, attendance, effectiveness of the events, and the proper use of resources. Successful event planning and execution can significantly boost the organization's reputation and influence. ③VG₃ is Member Development and Management: This indicator measures the organization's performance in recruiting, training, motivating, and managing its members. It focuses on members' growth opportunities, satisfaction, cohesion, and the organization's emphasis on talent development. Effective member management helps enhance the overall vitality and efficiency of the organization. ④VG₄ is Financial and Resource Management: This indicator evaluates the organization's ability in managing funds, budgeting, resource allocation, and securing external sponsorships. Transparent and reasonable financial management is crucial for the sustainable development of the organization, ensuring optimal use of resources and enhancing its credibility. The T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS approach is came up with the quality evaluation of management work in university student organizations.

Step 1. Construct the T2NN-matrix $VM = [VM_{ij}]_{5 \times 4}$ (Table 1).

Table 1. T2NN information

	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄
A ₁	{{(0.61, 0.65, 0.68), (0.12, 0.14, 0.19), (0.26, 0.29, 0.34)}}	{{(0.52, 0.57, 0.65), (0.13, 0.23, 0.26), (0.34, 0.39, 0.43)}}	{{(0.71, 0.74, 0.79), (0.06, 0.09, 0.18), (0.21, 0.24, 0.29)}}	{{(0.56, 0.59, 0.64), (0.09, 0.13, 0.17), (0.23, 0.27, 0.32)}}
A ₂	{{(0.64, 0.69, 0.74), (0.13, 0.17, 0.21), (0.21, 0.26, 0.29)}}	{{(0.61, 0.64, 0.69), (0.12, 0.14, 0.21), (0.29, 0.32, 0.39)}}	{{(0.76, 0.79, 0.84), (0.06, 0.09, 0.21), (0.17, 0.26, 0.32)}}	{{(0.59, 0.62, 0.67), (0.13, 0.16, 0.23), (0.26, 0.28, 0.35)}}
A ₃	{{(0.57, 0.61, 0.68), (0.09, 0.15, 0.17), (0.23, 0.27, 0.36)}}	{{(0.49, 0.57, 0.61), (0.14, 0.17, 0.23), (0.41, 0.46, 0.48)}}	{{(0.67, 0.72, 0.78), (0.15, 0.18, 0.24), (0.23, 0.27, 0.35)}}	{{(0.61, 0.64, 0.69), (0.09, 0.16, 0.19), (0.27, 0.32, 0.39)}}
A ₄	{{(0.71, 0.74, 0.79), (0.06, 0.12, 0.19), (0.26, 0.29, 0.34)}}	{{(0.63, 0.67, 0.75), (0.15, 0.18, 0.26), (0.34, 0.39, 0.43)}}	{{(0.73, 0.76, 0.83), (0.06, 0.09, 0.18), (0.21, 0.24, 0.29)}}	{{(0.68, 0.72, 0.74), (0.13, 0.17, 0.23), (0.27, 0.32, 0.39)}}

	(0.14), (0.16, 0.18, 0.24))	(0.21), (0.26, 0.29, 0.37))	(0.16), (0.21, 0.24, 0.36))	(0.21), (0.29, 0.31, 0.37))	
A ₅	{{(0.64, 0.67, 0.72), (0.09, 0.13, 0.17), (0.21, 0.24, 0.29))}	{{(0.56, 0.59, 0.64), (0.12, 0.14, 0.21), (0.31, 0.34, 0.39))}	{{(0.65, 0.69, 0.74), (0.13, 0.15, 0.19), (0.26, 0.29, 0.34))}	{{(0.51, 0.57, 0.64), (0.16, 0.19, 0.24), (0.29, 0.34, 0.39))}	

Step 2. Normalize the $VM = [VM_{ij}]_{5 \times 4}$ into $NVM = [NVM_{ij}]_{5 \times 4}$ (See Table 2).

Table 2. The normalized T2NN

	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄
A ₁	{{(0.61, 0.65, 0.68), (0.12, 0.14, 0.19), (0.26, 0.29, 0.34))}	{{(0.52, 0.57, 0.65), (0.13, 0.23, 0.26), (0.34, 0.39, 0.43))}	{{(0.71, 0.74, 0.79), (0.06, 0.09, 0.18), (0.21, 0.24, 0.29))}	{{(0.56, 0.59, 0.64), (0.09, 0.13, 0.17), (0.23, 0.27, 0.32))}
A ₂	{{(0.64, 0.69, 0.74), (0.13, 0.17, 0.21), (0.21, 0.26, 0.29))}	{{(0.61, 0.64, 0.69), (0.12, 0.14, 0.21), (0.29, 0.32, 0.39))}	{{(0.76, 0.79, 0.84), (0.06, 0.09, 0.21), (0.17, 0.26, 0.32))}	{{(0.59, 0.62, 0.67), (0.13, 0.16, 0.23), (0.26, 0.28, 0.35))}
A ₃	{{(0.57, 0.61, 0.68), (0.09, 0.15, 0.17), (0.23, 0.27, 0.36))}	{{(0.49, 0.57, 0.61), (0.14, 0.17, 0.23), (0.41, 0.46, 0.48))}	{{(0.67, 0.72, 0.78), (0.15, 0.18, 0.24), (0.23, 0.27, 0.35))}	{{(0.61, 0.64, 0.69), (0.09, 0.16, 0.19), (0.27, 0.32, 0.39))}
A ₄	{{(0.71, 0.74, 0.79), (0.06, 0.12, 0.14), (0.16, 0.18, 0.24))}	{{(0.63, 0.67, 0.75), (0.15, 0.18, 0.21), (0.26, 0.29, 0.37))}	{{(0.73, 0.76, 0.83), (0.06, 0.09, 0.16), (0.21, 0.24, 0.36))}	{{(0.68, 0.72, 0.74), (0.13, 0.17, 0.21), (0.29, 0.31, 0.37))}
A ₅	{{(0.64, 0.67, 0.72), (0.09, 0.13, 0.17), (0.21, 0.24, 0.29))}	{{(0.56, 0.59, 0.64), (0.12, 0.14, 0.21), (0.31, 0.34, 0.39))}	{{(0.65, 0.69, 0.74), (0.13, 0.15, 0.19), (0.26, 0.29, 0.34))}	{{(0.51, 0.57, 0.64), (0.16, 0.19, 0.24), (0.29, 0.34, 0.39))}

Step 3. Construct the weight numbers:

$$vw_1 = 0.3050, vw_2 = 0.2649, vw_3 = 0.2126, vw_4 = 0.2175.$$

Step 4. Construct the relative weight: $rvw = (1.0000, 0.8685, 0.6970, 0.7131)$

Step 5. Construct the $T2NNDDD = (T2NNDDD_{ij})_{5 \times 4}$ (Table 3):

Table 3. The $T2NNDDD = (T2NNDDD_{ij})_{5 \times 4}$

	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄
A ₁	-0.5501	-1.5901	0.5016	0.3532
A ₂	0.3827	1.2915	1.0613	1.0028
A ₃	-0.5423	-0.3691	-1.2326	-1.3470
A ₄	1.0586	-0.6864	-0.0190	-0.8512
A ₅	-2.1888	0.3269	-0.6540	-0.1814

Step 6. Construct the T2NNPIDS and T2NNNIDS (Table 4).

Table 4. T2NNPIDS and T2NNNIDS

	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄
T2NNPIDS	1.0586	1.2915	1.0613	1.0028
T2NNNIDS	-2.1888	-1.5901	-1.2326	-1.3470

Step 7. Construct the $T2NNEDV(VA_1, T2NNPIDS)$ and $T2NNEDV(VA_1, T2NNNIDS)$ (Table 5).

Table 5. $T2NNEDV(VA_1, T2NNPIDS)$ and $T2NNEDV(VA_1, T2NNNIDS)$

Alternative	$T2NNEDV(VA_1, T2NN)$	$T2NNEDV(VA_1, T2NN)$	$T2NNCCV(VA_1, T2NN)$	DS
A ₁	3.4098	2.9298	0.4621	
A ₂	0.6759	5.0695	0.8824	
A ₃	4.0130	2.0499	0.3381	
A ₄	2.9183	3.6168	0.5534	
A ₅	3.9775	2.3170	0.3681	

Step 8. Construct the $T2NNCCV(VA_1, T2NNPIDS)$ (See Table 5).

Step 9. In light with $T2NNCCV(VA_1, T2NNPIDS)$, the order is constructed as shown in Figure 2: $A_2 > A_4 > A_1 > A_5 > A_3$ and the optimal regional comprehensive university is A_2 .

Figure 2. The rank of alternatives.

4.2. Comparative analysis

The T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS technique is compared with T2NNWA technique [20], T2NNWG technique [20], T2NN-TOPSIS technique [20], T2NN-EDAS technique [25], T2NN-MABAC technique [26], T2NN-TODIM technique [27] and T2NN-TODIM-VIKOR approach [28]. The comparative results are constructed in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Order of different approaches

From the detailed analysis above, it can be observed that while the ranking order of different approaches may vary slightly, they consistently identify the same optimal and worst-performing regional comprehensive universities. This consistency confirms the effectiveness of the T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS for evaluating the quality of management work in university student organizations. The results demonstrate that the proposed method accurately captures both the best and worst cases, validating its reliability in handling such evaluations.

The major advantages of the T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS can be summarized as follows: ① Handling uncertainty and psychological behavior: The T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS approach not only manages the uncertainty inherent in the evaluation process but also takes into account the psychological behavior of decision-makers. This is particularly important in the context of evaluating management work in university student organizations, where subjective judgment and personal preferences often play a role. By integrating Type-2 Neutrosophic Numbers (T2NNs), the approach is able to represent fuzzy, uncertain information more effectively, providing a more accurate and nuanced evaluation. ② Combining the strengths of ExpTODIM and TOPSIS: The approach effectively blends the differing behaviors of ExpTODIM and TOPSIS when these two models are combined. ExpTODIM captures the decision-makers' risk preferences and psychological behavior, while TOPSIS focuses on ranking alternatives based on their distance from an ideal solution. By hybridizing these two methods, T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS provides a more comprehensive decision-making framework, capable of addressing both the risk-related and distance-based aspects of the evaluation.

In conclusion, the T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS approach offers a robust and reliable method for quality evaluation, managing uncertainty and psychological factors while leveraging the complementary strengths of ExpTODIM and TOPSIS. This makes it a valuable tool for decision-making in complex, multi-attribute scenarios such as the management of university student

organizations.

5. Managerial Implications

Evaluating the quality of management work in university student organizations has several managerial implications, such as:

- 1) **Enhancing Organizational Structure and Leadership Skills: Leadership Development:** Evaluations help identify gaps in student leadership skills, allowing university managers to implement training programs that focus on team management, decision-making, and effective communication. **Role Clarity and Accountability: Assessment of management work** highlights areas where responsibilities may be unclear, helping establish clear roles and accountability measures within the organization, reducing redundancy and improving efficiency.
- 2) **Improving Student Engagement and Satisfaction: Tailoring Activities to Student Interests:** Evaluation results can reveal what students value in their organizations. Managers can then guide organizations to design activities that better align with student interests, enhancing engagement and satisfaction. **Increasing Participation Rates: Insights into student preferences** allow managers to suggest program adjustments that attract and retain more students, thereby increasing participation and fostering a more vibrant campus community.
- 3) **Optimizing Resource Allocation and Utilization: Effective Budget Management:** Evaluating the quality of management work can highlight areas where resources are either underutilized or overspent, enabling managers to better allocate budgets and maximize the impact of available funds. **Efficient Use of Facilities and Resources: Assessments** help identify inefficiencies in resource usage, prompting student organizations to use university facilities, equipment, and materials more effectively.

6. Conclusion

The quality evaluation of management work in university student organizations is a systematic process of analyzing and assessing various aspects of the organization's management. The primary goal is to measure the management level, operational efficiency, and overall performance of student organizations through a scientific and reasonable evaluation system. Evaluation typically covers areas such as organizational system development, event planning and execution, member development and management, and financial and resource management. By combining both quantitative and qualitative methods, the evaluation not only highlights the strengths and weaknesses of the organization's management but also provides clear directions for future improvements. Effective quality evaluation helps enhance the operational efficiency of student organizations, strengthens team cohesion, and promotes sustainable development, thereby better serving the broader university student community. The quality evaluation of management work in university student organizations is MADM. The TODIM and TOPSIS methods have been applied to MADM. T2NNs are utilized to represent fuzzy data during quality evaluation of management

work in university student organizations. In this research, the T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS technique is proposed for MADM, incorporating T2NNs to handle uncertainty. A numerical example is provided to demonstrate the quality evaluation of management work in university student organizations, along with a comparative analysis that validates the effectiveness of the T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS approach. The primary research motivations for this study are outlined: (1) the ExpTODIM and TOPSIS methods are enhanced by integrating T2NNs; (2) entropy technique is used to assign weight values through score functions within the T2NN framework; (3) the T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS is introduced for MADM under T2NNs; and (4) a numerical example and comparative analysis are conducted to verify the validity of the T2NN-ExpTODIM-TOPSIS approach in evaluating the quality of management work in university student organizations. This approach provides an effective solution for addressing complex decision-making scenarios involving uncertainty and fuzzy information.

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